

THE SYMBOL OF ELEGANCE AND LOYALTY

Umarova Shoira Usmonovna

A history teacher at Karshi Vocational School

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6259952>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05th February 2022

Accepted: 10th February 2022

Online: 15th February 2022

KEY WORDS

*the Second World War
"Girls' Song" and "Poems"*

ABSTRACT

Zulfiya Isroilova is a well-known and talented Uzbek poet. She is a brilliant artist, a woman who felt the heart of ordinary people - a hard worker, and fought valiantly for the equal rights of Eastern women in society. Her life and work are an example for Uzbek women.

This year, on the first day of spring, marks the 107th anniversary of the birth of the Zulfiya who is the People's Poet of Uzbekistan, public figure, winner of the State Prize. In accordance with the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in 2014 her 100th anniversary was widely celebrated.

Can any soul enjoy like a handful of water after reading my poem.

Zulfiya Israilova was born on March 1, 1915 in Degriz mahalla of Tashkent in a family of craftsmen. The poetess wrote – “I am the daughter of a craftsman father and

Zulfiya
a woman who has spent her whole life in the same place”.

After receiving her primary education, the future poetess entered the Uzbek women's school in 1931. During her years of study,

her interest in literature and poetry grew. Along with examples of classical literature, she read with interest the works of writers and poets who were the famous representatives of that time, such as Sadridin Ayniy, Abdulla Qodiriy, Gayratiy, Oybek, Gafur Gulom, Hamid Olimjon, Oydin, Yashin, Uygun, she also practiced writing poems and stories. Her first works were published in the magazine named "New Way". Sadi A, was the first to comment on Zulfiya's poems, saying: "These poems also represent that this pencil was a step towards a fast-growing poet, more fast-growing ability". In fact, the idea has been proven. Shortly afterwards, in 1932, Zulfiya's first collection of poems "Leaves of Life" was published. To improve her knowledge and skills, the poetess studied at the Tashkent State Pedagogical Institute named after Nizami. In 1935, she entered the graduate school of the Institute of Language and Literature. From 1938 to 1940 she worked in the publishing house of children's and youth literature.

By 1939, two more collections of Zulfiya's "Girls' Song" and "Poems" were published.

During the Second World War, the courage and perseverance of our people, both on the front of war and behind the war was an inspiration for the poet. She skillfully expressed the events, feelings and experiences of our compatriots. Although Zulfiya had been the head of the fiction department at the Uzbek State Publishing House since 1941, she had been very productive. In 1943, his collections of poetry were published in Russian "Vernost" ("Loyalty"), and in 1944 in Uzbek "In the days of Hijrah".

Zulfiya's works such as "My Homeland", "Wearing overcoat with a gun in my hand", "Wait for us", "He was called Farhad" are

the best examples of wartime Uzbek poetry. As you read her poems, it is easy to see what excited her at a particular time, what she felt in her life, and how her life changed. Indeed, In 1944, on July 3 Zulfiya suffered a tragic loss, her husband, Hamid Olimjon died in an accident. Most of her works were written between 1944 and 1947 and they were based on the theme of Nostalgia and Love, and this was the effect of her loss in her poems. Poems written during this period, such as "In the days of Hijrah", "Sorry, I was in ignorance", "Star", "What happened to you", "Where are you, my heart?", "Have you seen tears in my eyes", seem sad and gloomy. However, they leave a bright impression on the reader with a high melody of feelings of fidelity and devotion.

Nuisance don't let open my eyes
Burning my head if I put the head
Can't soothe neither book nor pen
My verses begin moaning

In the poem "Ne baloga etding muftalo" the poet describes her sufferings in such way, and in the poem "Spring has come to ask you" the poet expresses her feelings of nostalgia and love through the season of spring for the person she loves.

Zulfiya's 1947 "Hulkar", 1950 "I sing the morning", 1953 "Conversation with friends", Oydin Sabirova, 1958 "People close to my heart", 1959 "Selected works", 1958 "Lyudi blizki moemu serdse" , 1959 "Stixi" and more than a dozen collections of poetry have been published in Uzbek and Russian languages.

From 1950, Zulfiya was the head of the department of the magazine called "Women of Uzbekistan" for three years, and from 1954 to the end of her life she worked as an editor-in-chief of the

magazine "Saodat". Her essays and articles which were published on social pages such as "Meeting with a Woman in Paranja", "Conversation with Friends", "Conversation Continues", "Colombo Pigeons", "Memories of Yugoslavia", "Together Forward" were focus on the social issues of that time, and undermine her talent in journalism.

Zulfiya also took an active part in public affairs. She has been to several foreign countries. In 1956, She spoke at the Asian-African Writers' Conference which was held in Delhi and she suggested to hold the next conference in Tashkent. Her poem "Mushoira" was the product of the impressions of this conference, which glorifies the friendship and peace of nations. This poem has been translated into many languages.

Literary translation, one of the main means of international literary relations, also plays an important role in Zulfiya's work. She had skillfully translated the centuries of famous artists such as Nekrasov, Lesya Ukrainka, Solomey Perves, Silva Kaputiyan, Marvarid Dilbozi into Uzbek. Hamid Olimjon's opera libretto based on the epic "Zaynab and Omon" and her staging of the epic "Semurig" for the youth theater in collaboration with S. Somova also testify to Zulfiya's versatility.

The effective creative and social activity of the poetess was appreciated and respected. In particular, in 1965 she was awarded the title of People's Poet of Uzbekistan. In 1967 she won the Jawaharlal Nehru International Prize and in 1970 the "Nilufar" International Prize. In 1972, she was awarded the 1st degree of Order of Cyril and Mefodiy of the Bulgarian People's Republic. In 1976, she was awarded the Zulfiya State Prize for her book of poems

"Rainbow". In 1984, she was awarded the title of Hero of Labor.

Although a brutal death took away the talented poetess of the Uzbek people on August 1, 1996, she remained forever on the poetry scene with her work.

Zulfiya was a deep thinker, a passionate word artist and an active public figure. For fifty years she had made an invaluable contribution to the development of Uzbek literature with her multifaceted and unique work. During the years of independence, the services of the poetess have been recognized and appreciated by our state. The establishment of the Zulfiya State Prize on June 10, 1999 by the Decree of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan was a significant event. Since then, the award has been presented annually to girls who have excelled in science, culture, literature, art and education. In 2007, a statue of the poet was erected in Tashkent.

This monument is a symbol of our people's love and respect for Zulfiya. However, she left an indelible mark on herself with her indestructible work and her great contribution to the development of our literature.

TERMS

Degriz - is a blacksmith who makes various household tools by casting steel and melting cast iron.

Postgraduate education - is an integral part of the education system, the preparation of highly qualified and scientific pedagogical candidates

Opera libretto - (Italian) - a book of musical dramatic works.

Mushoira (Arabic) Poetry Competition.

Conference - (Latin) - gathering

Journalism (Latin) social - A type of literary work devoted to socio-political and current issues.

REFERENCES:

1. "High spirituality is an invincible force." I. Karimov.
2. "History of Uzbek literature". I. O. Sultonov.
3. "Vernost". Zulfiya. Tashkent. 1943.
4. "School of mastery". Tashkent. 1960.
5. "Selected works". Zulfiya. Tashkent. 1959.
6. "About my loved ones and friends". Zulfiya. Culture of Uzbekistan. 1958.
7. "Remembering Zulfiya" Joraboyeva Sh.
8. "Uzbek writers". Miraliyev. R. Shokirova. Tashkent.
9. "PF-2326-son 10.06.1999. On supporting the establishment of the Zulfiya State Prize. "
10. "Poems, Fragments of Memory" Zulfiya.
11. "I miss you sister" Ozod Sharafiddinov. 1995.
12. "About sister Zulfiya". N.Karimov.